

Suspended culture of the Manabí oyster *Crassostrea* cf. *corteziensis* in a tropical estuary

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ABSTRACT

Grow-out of the Manabí oyster (*Crassostrea* cf. *corteziensis*) under suspended culture conditions from the Chone River Estuary (Manabí, Ecuador) was evaluated. The culture was established in lanterns with 50 oysters/floor for seven months (July 2022 to February 2023) using juveniles (34.9±6.2 mm) collected from natural oyster beds in the same estuary. The growth and survival, as well as environmental variables in the culture site, were monitored. The growth in the shell dimension was continuous, reaching high rates during October and November. At the end of the study, 86.7±6.68 mm anteroposterior length, 110.7±19.04 g dry mass of the whole organism (with 3.7±0.67 g soft tissue), and survival of 92.6±2.62 % were obtained. No association was observed between the patterns of the growth curves and those of the environmental parameters; however, the decrease of body mass (during February 2023) was associated with increased temperature, decreased salinity, and lower phytoplankton content. Oysters of marketable size (80 mm) were obtained after seven months of culture. The results suggest the biological feasibility of cultivating the Manabí oyster *C. cf. corteziensis* in the Chone River Estuary, which could be an emerging species for aquaculture in Ecuador and the tropical American Pacific.

1. Introduction

In the tropical American Pacific, the main oyster cultivated is *Magallana gigas* (Thunberg 1793), formerly *Crassostrea gigas* (Thunberg 1793), a species introduced for aquaculture purposes, followed in smaller proportion by the native species *Crassostrea corteziensis* (Hertlein 1951) (Lodeiros et al., 2018; Chávez-Villalba et al., 2021). However, other oyster species could be used to increase their production through aquaculture such as *Crassostrea columbiensis*, and for less common oysters, *Striostrea palmula*, *Ostrea conchaphila*, *Undulostrea megodon*, *Ostrea*

angelica, and *Crassostrea* spp.; where it is necessary to clarify its taxonomic identification (Lodeiros et al., 2020; Chávez-Villalba et al., 2021).

In the Chone River Estuary, province of Manabí, Ecuador, there are natural banks of a wild oyster of the genus *Crassostrea*, commonly called "Manabí oyster", which inhabits mangrove and rocky bottom ecosystems that is the object of fishing extraction for consumption and local commercialization (Panta-Vélez et al., 2023). This oyster species has not been precisely identified; nevertheless, it has been the subject of taxonomic and morphological evaluation and shows a shell-like *Crassostrea corteziensis*, *Crassostrea aequatorialis* (d'Orbigny 1846), and *Crassostrea*

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columbiensis (Hanley 1846) described by Coan and Valentich (2012) and Brito-Vera and Mora (2016). Preliminary studies of molecular analyses show a low genetic relationship with other species of the family Ostreidae, suggesting that it has no specific sequence records in Gene Bank (GB), and/or is a new species to scientific knowledge (Lodeiros et al., 2020). For this study, we agreed to name the Manabí oyster as *Crassostrea cf. corteziensis*.

Aquaculture cycles of different bivalve species up to commercial sizes have been evaluated in the Chone River estuary, including *Magallanas gigas* and *Pteria sterna* (Espinoza-Vera et al., 2023, Treviño et al., 2020). This estuary has important hydrobiological characteristics for bivalve growth and fattening, particularly in the dry season, since the influence of rains leads to low salinity and environmental changes that reduce the feasibility of cultivation (Álvarez-García et al., 2021, Loján-Avellán et al., 2021).

The Manabí oyster is frequently consumed as fresh or frozen meat and is regionally processed in specific dishes in restaurants. Recent studies on the populational, physiological, and biological characterization of the Manabí oyster are being carried out to undertake actions for its management as a natural resource, and to evaluate the possibility of its production through aquaculture activities (Lodeiros et al., 2020; Panta-Vélez et al., 2023; Falconí et al. 2024); preliminary reports consider that its extraction is decreasing due to overfishing. For this reason, the present study evaluates the feasibility of the grow-out of the Manabí oyster *C. cf. corteziensis* under suspended culture conditions in tropical estuaries from where this species is native.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Oyster culture

Juvenile oysters (34.9 ± 6.22 mm length) of Manabí oyster *C. cf. corteziensis* were manually collected from natural beds in the coastal area located near Bahía de Caráquez, province of Manabí, Ecuador ($0^{\circ}36'23.28''$ S; $80^{\circ}25'22.62''$ W) in an area that corresponds to the middle estuary with a mixture of fresh and saltwater (Fairbridge, 1980; Arriaga et al., 1999). The oysters were kept in lantern nets suspended from a floating dock for four days as an acclimatization period.

The experimental culture was carried out over seven months (from 28 July 2022–28 February 2023), starting with a density of 50 oysters/floor, equivalent to an occupation of 50 % of the available area on each lantern floor. The study was performed in triplicate using five-story lantern nets (42 cm diameter, 20 cm height between floors, 20 mm mesh size). In each lantern net, the intermediate floor was considered an experimental replicate and the others as reserves, as they were used to replace the organisms removed during samplings.

2.2. Survival and biometric parameters

Survival was recorded monthly by counting the live organisms in each replicate, and 10 oysters were randomly sampled to measure their maximum anteroposterior length (umbo to shell margin), ventral dorsum (axis perpendicular to the anteroposterior), and between valves. During the first four months on a bimonthly and then monthly basis, 5 oysters were taken from each experimental replicate to determine the dry mass of adductor muscle, soft tissue, and shell, using a balance with 0.001 g precision, after a dehydration period of 48 h at 65 °C.

2.3. Environmental parameters

At the culture site, water temperature was determined with an electronic thermograph (Hobo, USA) programmed to record every 5 minutes. Intra-weekly, water transparency was measured with a Secchi disk, and a sample of 500 mL of superficial water was taken to determine salinity with a refractometer, followed by fixing a water sample with Lugol until a slight amber coloration developed to count

and identify phytoplankton under a 400X binocular microscope, using the drip technique according to Semina (1978).

2.4. Statistical analysis

The data of the variables analyzed showed a normal distribution and homogeneous variances, according to the Shapiro-Wilks and Leven tests (Zar, 2010). A one-way ANOVA was used to differentiate the averages on the growth parameters, considering time or sampling as a factor. Differences between treatments were determined according to Tukey *a posteriori* analysis. For all tests, the significance level was $P=0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Survival and biometric parameters

During the study period, high survival of the oysters in culture was recorded, with mortality only observed from August to December. At the end of the study, a cumulative survival of 92.6 ± 2.60 % was obtained (Fig. 1).

The growth obtained as a function of shell dimension was generally continuous (Fig. 2), with a significant increase during November 2022, particularly in the anteroposterior length and likewise in February 2023 concerning the length between shells. At the end of the study, the experimental organisms reached average lengths of 86.7 ± 6.68 , 61.0 ± 1.02 , and 44.0 ± 0.89 mm in anteroposterior, dorsoventral, and between valves lengths, respectively.

The growth in shell dry mass was continuous with high rates starting in December (Fig. 3a) reaching 110.7 ± 19.04 g of dry mass. Tissue biomass, both in adductor muscle and other remaining tissues, showed a continuous growth pattern, except in the last month of the study (February 2023) when it showed no significant differences from the values reached in January 2022 (Fig. 3b). At the end of the study, mean biomass of 3.7 ± 0.67 g of total soft tissue was recorded, with 16 % corresponding to muscle (0.60 ± 0.06 g) and 84 % to other tissues (3.1 ± 0.61 g).

3.2. Environmental factors

The average daily water temperature at the culture site oscillated between 24.5 and 29 °C (Fig. 4a). From the beginning of the experiment until October, the temperature ranged between 24.5 and 26.5 °C, followed by a sustained increasing trend until the end of the study when maximum temperatures were recorded (January-February 2023). The minimum and maximum ranges of the intraday temperature values generally ranged between 2 and 2.5 °C and not exceeding 4 °C. Salinity (Fig. 4b) showed relatively stable behavior from the start of cultivation (July 2022) to mid-October 2022 (28–35 ‰) with a moderate decrease

Fig. 1. Survival (%) of the Manabí oyster *Crassostrea cf. corteziensis* under suspended culture conditions (from June 2022 to February 2023) in the Chone River Estuary, Manabí, Ecuador. The results present the mean \pm confidence intervals (95 %).

Fig. 2. Shell dimension growth (anteroposterior, dorsoventral and between valves) of the Manabí oyster *Crassostrea cf. corteziensis* under suspended culture conditions (from June 2022 to February 2023) from Chone River Estuary, Manabí, Ecuador. The results present the mean \pm confidence intervals (95 %).

Fig. 3. Mass of the Shell (a) and soft tissues of (b) showing the total, muscle and the rest of the tissues of the Manabí oyster *Crassostrea cf. corteziensis* under suspended culture conditions from Chone River Estuary, Manabí, Ecuador. The results present the mean \pm confidence intervals (95 %).

to 22.5 ‰, and another abrupt decrease to 7 ‰ from early to late February 2023. The recorded values of water transparency (Fig. 4c) ranged from 35 to 120 cm, with a general increasing trend towards the middle of the experimental period, maintaining generally high values (>80 cm), to decrease at the end of February and remained with low values until the end of the experiment (30–60 cm).

The density of total phytoplankton cells was variable, showing two peaks of elevated concentrations (>50,000 cells/mL) during September 2022 and from late November to mid-January 2023 (Fig. 5). Values recorded were low in October and early November (7000 cells/mL) and by the end of the study the density increased to 12,000–25,000 cells/mL. Phytoplankton was mostly composed of diatoms (~80 %), followed by cyanophytes (16 %), and chlorophytes (4 %).

Fig. 4. Temperature (a), salinity (b) and water transparency (c) in the experimental culture area from Chone River Estuary, Manabí, Ecuador.

Fig. 5. Availability of live food expressed as density of phytoplankton (cells mL⁻¹ × 1000) and composition (%) by groups in the experimental culture area.

4. Discussion

The present study has generated basic scientific and technological knowledge, providing potentially applicable information for the suspended culture of the Manabí oyster *C. cf. corteziensis* from ~35 mm wild juveniles collected at a natural bank, showing the biological feasibility of culturing it in the estuary of the Chone River, Manabí, Ecuador. In general, growth was continuous in shell and soft tissue, with typical exponential behavior, except for the last month of culture (February 2023), when there was no increase in tissue mass. This growth recess coincided with the highest average daily temperatures (~29°C) and intraday variability with values up to 31°C, as well as an abrupt decrease in salinity from ~30‰ to 7‰, which may have produced physiological stress (Falconí et al. 2024). Under these conditions, shell growth appears to be unaffected, since growth did not stop, and this could be probably related to the lower energy requirement for shell production, relative to the higher energy expenditure required for soft tissue production (Thompson and MacDonald, 1991, Graham et al., 2019).

Water transparency is an environmental variable related to phytoplankton productivity and the availability of particulate organic matter used as food for filter-feeding molluscs. This parameter showed great variability (35–120 cm) and no definite pattern was observed throughout the study. However, the availability of food in the Chone River Estuary did not seem to be a limiting factor for oyster culture, since the cell concentration remained generally high (>10,000 cells/mL) and even though during November–January minimum values were recorded (1300–6300 cells/mL), oyster growth did not stop. During this study, diatoms were more abundant (~80 %) in the available phytoplankton. These microalgae contribute to the better development of the bivalve (Yusoff and Wong, 2023). This allows us to hypothesize that the quality of the available food could be one of the factors associated with the growth of the Manabí oyster under cultural conditions in the Chone River Estuary as was also shown by *Magallana gigas* (Treviño et al., 2020).

The culture was developed during the equatorial dry season when there was not much influence of rain and salinity remained in a range of ~25–30, and just to the initial rainy season, characterized particularly by high temperatures and by torrential rains that brought large volumes of freshwater leading to the decline in salinity (Leal-Filho et al., 2022). The results showed that the low salinity could negatively affect soft tissue growth, but not necessarily oyster survival. The biological feasibility for the cultivation of the Manabí oyster in the Chone River Estuary is considered appropriate, since other oysters under culture in the area, such as *Magallana gigas* or the pearl oyster *Pteria sterna*, experience high mortalities when they are exposed to low salinity (Treviño et al., 2020; Lucas-Zambrano et al., 2023). However, it is necessary to generate information throughout the rainy season and to evaluate the physiological and technological processes of the culture to determine its economic feasibility, for validation and continued productive scaling-up purposes.

In the Chone River estuary, the Manabí oyster exhibits average growth reaching a commercial size of approximately 80 mm one year after hatching (Panta-Velez et al., 2023). Although the present study shows that commercial size can be achieved in about 7 months, indicating a higher growth rate for oysters in suspended culture, the growth rate could be considered similar to that of natural populations if the initial 5 months needed to reach the starting sizes of this study (~35 mm) are taken into account. This includes the larval and post-larval stages and the growth until reaching juvenile size, considering the development of the oyster during low salinity periods (rainy season), which could result in reduced growth rate. Comparative studies with smaller organisms in suspended culture and natural populations over an annual period, encompassing the dry and rainy seasons, are necessary to validate this hypothesis.

Comparing other species of oysters cultured in the tropic, Lodeiros et al. (2018) have reported that *Magallana gigas* reached commercial size

(80 mm) at 10–11 months of cultivation in Ayangué, Santa Elena province, Ecuador. This is a slower growth than that reported for ostreids in the Mexican subtropics (Chávez-Villalba et al., 2021), like the *M. gigas* cultures conducted in lagoons in Sinaloa, Mexico (Navachiste-Macapule), where it can reach commercial size in eight months of culture (Rodríguez-Quiroz et al., 2016). However, Treviño et al. (2020) report *M. gigas* reached commercial size in only five months in the Chone River Estuary, with higher results for the Pacific oyster compared to the Manabí oyster.

Indeed, the Treviño et al. (2020) data from *M. gigas* suspended culture in the Chone River presents a higher growth in anteroposterior shell length (0.41 mm d⁻¹), while the performance of the Manabí oyster is significantly lower (0.25 mm d⁻¹). However, the shell mass growth of the Manabí oyster is more than double (0.49 g d⁻¹) than that of *M. gigas* (0.28 g d⁻¹), and similarly concerning the dry mass of tissues (Manabí oyster: 0.016 g d⁻¹ and *M. gigas*: 0.011 g d⁻¹). At commercial size (80 mm) the dry mass of the tissue in the Manabí oyster reached 3.5 g, representing 94 % more mass than that achieved by *M. gigas* (1.8). This higher mass production, particularly of soft tissue (meat), suggests that the commercial size of the Manabí oyster could be smaller (e.g. 70 mm), reducing the culture time. With the results of the present study, it is estimated that a dry mass of tissue of ~ 2.5 g, equivalent to about 10–11 g of wet mass, could be considered sufficient for commercial oysters (Betanzos-Vega et al., 2018).

At the end of the present study, the ratio of shells to anteroposterior shell length was 0.42, much higher than that recorded for *M. gigas*, almost doubling the suggested minimum value (0.25), indicating a concave morphology suitable for commercialization (Brake et al., 2003; Mizuta and Wikfors, 2019). The concavity in the Manabí oyster shell allows for a pit or indentation that the soft body of the oysters must occupy, producing a greater amount of meat. This suggests that, given its more globular and round morphology, without losing the elongated shape, the Manabí oyster is included in the group of cupped oysters of interest for aquaculture (Davis et al., 2021; Bhattacharjya et al., 2023).

Additionally, the results of the present study showed a high survival (>90 %) at seven months of culture, higher than that reported for *M. gigas* (71.5 %) at the end of the grow-out period in the same site and under similar suspended culture conditions (Treviño et al., 2020). This difference may be because the Manabí oyster is a natural inhabitant of the Chone River Estuary and it is possibly better adapted to changes in the environmental factors of the estuary throughout the year, including the rainy season, which can make its cultivation viable at larger scale aquaculture production.

Based on the above, it is possible to assume that there is potential and biological feasibility for the cultivation of the Manabí oyster *C. cf. corteziensis* in the Chone River Estuary, which could be an emerging species for aquaculture in Ecuador and the tropical American Pacific. Its tolerance to low salinity allows considering the possibility of its use in multi-trophic culture systems in *Penaeus vannamei* shrimp farms (Mazón-Suástegui et al., 2022), given that the greatest productive development of this crustacean takes place in low salinity conditions. This could add items to make the co-culture of both species viable, considering the ecosystem services of the Manabí oyster in terms of reduced eutrophication and the shell due to its thick, robust and usable shell to obtain by-products such as calcium carbonate (Morris et al., 2019), also bivalve farming provides a source of protein with the lowest human-produced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which produces important environmental services (Zavell et al., 2023), which is compatible with the blue economy in the face of global climate change.

Given the above, further studies should be directed towards the optimization of oyster culture, along with the development of mass seed production in a controlled laboratory environment, since there is no published evidence on the technical and economic feasibility of massively collecting wild seed from the environment. Likewise, since the taxonomic identification of the Manabí oyster is uncertain, its taxonomic identification through molecular techniques is necessary for further

studies.

Ethical statement

All procedures followed ethical and responsible research guidelines using *in vivo* animals for experiments (Kilkenny et al., 2010).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Patricia Aguilar-Román: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **José Manuel Mazón-Suástegui:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Jorge Vélez-Falcones:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Luis Treviño:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alan García-Bermúdez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Edgar Zapata Vívienes:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **César Lodeiros:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elizabeth Ati:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Yuber Añazco-Correa:** Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization of the experimental design, drafting, revising, and editing of the final manuscript were performed by César Lodeiros, José Manuel Mazón and Edgar Zapata-Vívienes. Conducting the experiments, laboratory analysis, research data management, maintenance activities, and writing the initial draft were performed by Elizabeth F. Ati, Yuber A. Añazco-Correa, Jorge Vélez-Falcones and Luis Treviño. The laboratory analyses of phytoplankton and manuscript revision were performed by Patricia Aguilar-Román. Management activities to produce metadata and maintain research data were performed by Alan García. Statistical analyses were performed by Alan García and Edgar Zapata-Vívienes

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